

THE SPECIFICITY OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION TO ITSELF (GENDER), THE INCIDENCE OF PRIMARY CLINICAL SIGNS IN PATIENTS AND THE PRESENCE OF PSYCHOEMOTIONAL DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

Patients with Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) have experienced a lot of psychoemotional disorders and put people in depression. The power of my organism to fight the disease was studied in a psychological state. The disease was analyzed by the Fergana region, depending on gender, age, initial clinical signs.

Relevance: Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) the study that the disease is in a gender-specific state among the people shows that each doctor needs a specific tactical criterion in treatment measures. We know that chronic stress can cause psychosomatic complications. The disease Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) is accompanied by a psychoemotional disorder. It has been observed that the disease Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) is accompanied by a gender-specific and psychoemotional disorder among our people but, not fully studied. So is the relevance of the topic. Many diseases affect the mental state of a person by affecting the clinical course. We would not be mistaken if we say that Coronavirus disease also creates the basis for the occurrence of a psychosomatic disorder.

Gender-specific perception from the second side of the disease requires hormonal disruptions and an individual approach to the treatment of patients and necessitates the study of gender-specific incidence of the disease in patients. That's also the relevance of the chosen topic.

Purpose of the study:

- 1-To assess the level of gender-specific prevalence of coronavirus disease among people and to determine the manifestation of initial clinical signs in patients.
- 2-study of psychoemotional disorders in those identified with Covid-19 infection.

Research materials and methods:

- 1-Patients with Covid-19 infection who applied to Fergana regional infectious diseases hospital and Margilan infectious diseases hospital.
- 2-Those who have been diagnosed with Covid-19 have psychoemotional disorders to perform a Sung test in order to identify depression in patients.

Research results. Gender-specific distribution of patients with Covid-19 disease.

1-Photo. Covid-19 initial clinical complaints in patients in the mid-severe evening.

2-Photo. GENDER DEPENDENCE OF PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOEMOTIONAL DISORDERS.

3-Photo

Conclusion: in 70 (52.2%) of patients with Covid-19, men were more likely to get sick. The cause of the disease is considered to be a traumatic habit. In our patients with 2nd Caronavirus, primary clinical signs varied, out of which 90 (48.9 %) came with complaints of upper respiratory tract prevailed. The pathological process in the respiratory system means dif-diagnosis with other diseases. 3-according to the result of the psychoemotional test, psychic stress caused the disease to stretch. It was found that bears hurt more. And this means the study of practical and theoretical knowledge of the genetic factor.

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